
INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN KG TO PG

C. S. Mitter ^{*1}

^{*1} Head and Associate Professor, Department of Zoology, Sathaye College, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India

Abstract:

Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) have become significant commodities in all aspects of life of all age groups in human beings. ICT's have revolutionized the field of food sector, companies, banking sector, health, IT sector, social media etc. Use of ICT in the classrooms of Kindergarten (KG) to Post Graduate (PG) can create innovative atmosphere which reduces the distance between the teachers and students. ICTs help to monitor and evaluate various activities such as exams, admissions, evaluations, results, teaching, alumni network, day to day office work, records of staff and students attendance etc. This work is an attempt to make understand ICT is useful in KG to PG to enhance the quality education.

Keywords: *ICT; Revolutionized; Innovative; Monitor and Enhance.*

Cite This Article: C. S. Mitter. (2018). "INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN KG TO PG." *International Journal of Engineering Technologies and Management Research*, 5(3), 226-229. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1218188.

1. Introduction

Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) provide access to information by means of telecommunication tools. It is a combination of hardware and software equipped with service and information [1]. In the 21st century, information has become a major economic entity which can be converted into knowledge in the field of education [2]. ICT is one of the most potential means of KG to PG education. World has moved from traditional education methods to modern technology education. Modern technologies have brought critical change in education. ICT has the potential to "bridge the knowledge gap" in terms of improving quality education [3]. The use of ICT has enabled teachers to reach students across the borders and students from developing countries can also access advanced educational courses. Online education is flexible, affordable, eco-friendly and nature- friendly due to paperless classrooms. Google classrooms are easily accessible through android mobile handsets and laptop which have become very common in education system. The provision of the ICT enhances the teaching process and continuous monitoring of students' progress in schools and colleges [4]. Higher education provides an opportunity to reflect on the various social issues. It contributes the national development through specialized knowledge and skills. The National Policy on Education (NPE) 1986, revised in 1992 states that in higher education in general and technical education in particular, steps will be taken to facilitate inter-regional mobility by providing equal access to every Indian

of requisite merit regardless his origin. Information literacy means a mastery of the process of becoming informed by means of ICT [5].

Government has a systematic planning in education. The national education policy (NEP) has constructed the draft which was published in 2016, K. Kasturiranjana committee was appointed to redraft the policy, which was expected in December 2017. The policy is prepared by a panel headed by former Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO) K. Kasturiranjana. NEP 2017 has retrieved many points from NEP 2016 which was drafted by TSR Subramaniam committee. Along with number of points, use of ICT in education is insisted for better performance for student's teachers and administrators.

2. Methodology

This work is done by investigating secondary data like e-journals, research data from website, books, proceedings etc.

3. Objectives

- To analyze KG to PG old and modern education method
- Why KG to PG education need ICT tools
- Emerging trends in KG to PG education

ICT – Student Friendly

From young age, students get exposure to ICTs which is very helpful to create interest and boost student's knowledge towards education.

Learning becomes very effective with fun and joy. It encourages active participation in learning process. Different forms of ICT tools increase ability to study on innovative ideas. It encourages individual learning which makes the students dynamic personality. Broad range of information can be easily accessed to convert information to knowledge which is useful in research oriented fields. Classrooms with ICTs can develop skills among students and teachers which is essential for modern communication. It motivates student's leadership and increases productivity of teachers and students.

ICT – Teacher-Friendly

It improves teacher's ability to teach and saves time and energy of teacher fraternity. ICT facilitates confidence and enthusiasm with IT tools skills.

ICT – Parents Friendly

ICT provides easy way to communicate with educational institutions about their wards. ICT provides wards attendance reports results and progress from time to time without visiting schools or colleges and meet teachers and this saves time.

Flipped Classroom

Recorded lectures, presentations, demonstrations, are uploaded on YouTube for students to access. These can be accessed by KG to PG students who often remain absent in the lectures for

chalk duster method due to various reasons like games, competition, illness, can get lectures available by this method. It is a homogenous blend, out of class and in-class activity which provides complete freedom to students by the teachers [6]. Blended learning has been gaining acceptance for effective learning in KG to PG education. These are the emerging trends in KG to PG education.

It enhances quality and accessibility of education. It increases flexibility of learners because learners can access information according to their free time.

It is a teacher's duty to inspire and motivate the students and assist them in their quest for knowledge and skills. ICT is one of the major factors in KG to PG education which can bring a rapid change in the nature of education [7]. Teachers are already overloaded with problems such as managing large number of students per classroom and non-teaching work, oral exams, tutorials, paper setting, written exams, paper corrections, results related work, to focus on students interests, emotional and growing age related issues etc. To simplify such difficulties teachers should be able to use ICT with ease.

From KG level if ICT started than future teachers will be perfectly techno savvy. Gradually teacher-centric approach will be replaced towards learner-centric approach by using ICT at KG level. At early age children are exposed to ICT tools like mobiles, TV, tablets, video games, education material etc at home. So it will be easy and interesting leaning with ICT for the children at school. In today's teaching-learning system, student's bags are overloaded with books, notebooks and other study material which has created a health problem at early age. With ICT tools this problem will be vanished permanently. ICT has the potential to breach KG to PG education for today and for better tomorrow. Video lectures, flipped classroom methodology, Google classroom, e-learning etc provide very interesting and comprehensive study material. So teachers can afford more time for interactions and for guide as per students need. The use of ICT required in education for KG to PG because children are more active in all technological tools.

4. Conclusion

ICT is prevalent in KG to PG. ICT tools play very crucial role in all sectors including educational institutions. Directly or indirectly all world depends on ICT for day to day activities. ICT provides systematic, scientific way of teaching. ICT is teacher-students and parents friendly device. It enhances quality education in KG to PG.

Implementation of ICT in all education sectors will save time, money and energy. ICTs make learners more attentive towards education with fun and joy. Access to ICTs gibes students and teachers a broad range of resources according to their needs.

Secondary data- Students are not finding lectures interesting, they just go to college to meet friends. Students mention faculties are not techno savvy and not updated to current market situation. They say they attend college to get degree and join coaching classes to get knowledge [8]

References

- [1] Yuen. A.H.K. (2010) “Blended learning in higher education: An exploration of teaching approaches” Proceeding of the 18th International conference on computer education.
- [2] Bhattacharjee. B. and Deb. K. (2016) “Role of ICT in 21st Century’s Teacher education”http://www.ripublication.com/ijeisv6n1_01.pdf.
- [3] Bali. R. (2017) “Using ICT for quality in teaching-learning and evaluation process”. NAAC sponsored National seminar, proceedings. At Pillai College of Arts, Commerce and Science, New Panvel- New Mumbai
- [4] Rao. V.S. N. (2017) “Role of ICT in enhancing teaching, learning and evaluation” NAAC sponsored National seminar, proceedings. At Pillai College of Arts, Commerce and Science, New Panvel- New Mumbai.
- [5] Moore, (2002) “An analysis of information literacy education”. Prague. Retrieved from <http://www.nclis.Gov/libinter/infolitconfandmeet/paper/moore-fullpaper.pdf>.
- [6] Jon B. and Sams Aaron (2012) “The Flipped Classroom” CSE Vol. 17.<http://www.lite.unesco.org>
- [7] Nagoba, B. S. and Mantri, S. B.(2015) “Role of teachers in quality enhancement in higher education” Journal of Krishna institute of Medical sciences University,4(1),177-182.National Knowledge Commission India (2007).Report to the nation 2006.Government of India. www.wordpress.com
- [8] Puranik,A. M. (2017) “Study of required paradigm shift in higher education: Need and its preparedness” NAAC sponsored National seminar, proceedings. At Pillai College of Arts, Commerce and Science, New Panvel- New Mumbai. Pp.69-74.

*Corresponding author.

E-mail address: chhayamitter@yahoo.co.in/chhayamitter@gmail.com